

Evaluation of Molluscicidal Activity of *Croton microstachyus* and *Cissus quadrangularis* against *Biomphalaria* and *Bulinus* Species of Snails

**Eyob Y. Garoy¹, Tsegezeab Goje¹, Dawit Mebrahtu¹, Atul Kaushik^{2*},
Robel Asfaha¹, Amanuel Andemariam¹, Dawit Brhane¹, Ermias Efreem¹,
Kiros Teweldebrhan¹ and Zere Araya¹**

¹School of Allied Health Professions, Asmara College of Health Sciences, 118 Adi Shimagle,
Asmara, 8566, Eritrea.

²School of Pharmacy, Asmara College of Health Sciences, 118 Adi Shimagle, Asmara, 8566, Eritrea.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Authors EYG and TG designed the study. Authors DM and AK wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors RA, AA, DB, EE, KT and ZA managed the experimental work and screening. Author DM managed the literature searches and supervision of extraction process. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The study was carried out to investigate the molluscicidal activities of different solvent extracts of two (spaceing) Eritrean local plants, *Croton macrostachyus* and *Cissus quadrangularis* identified using ethno-botanical, pharmacological information and also traditional use gathered from traditional healers.

Methods: Various solvent extract concentrations of leaves of *Croton macrostachyus* and *Cissus quadrangularis* leaves and seeds were tested for their molluscicidal activity against adult *Biomphalaria* species, the intermediate host of *S. mansoni* and *Bulinus* species, the intermediate host of *S. haematobium* and *S. intercalates*. The LC50 and LC90 were determined at 24 hours of

*Corresponding author: E-mail: atul_kaushik29@rediffmail.com;

exposure. Comparison of molluscicidal activity of the different solvent extracts within and among the plants was also done. The effect of the increase in exposure time (36 and 48 hrs) on molluscicidal activity of the plants with respect to each solvent extract was then assessed.

Results and Discussion: Screening test results indicated that a significant molluscicidal activity ranging from 15.558 ppm to 289.689 ppm was found. Comparison of the solvent extracts also revealed that a significant difference was shown in all the three plant materials, with p-value less than 0.05. Half (50%) of the plant extracts were found to have a significant difference in their molluscicidal activity upon increase in exposure time ($p < 0.05$). In general, comparison of the plant material extracts showed that *Croton marostachyus* seed has the highest molluscicidal activity.

Conclusion: From the observations, it is concluded that plants, *Croton macrostachyus* leaf, seed and *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf were found to have molluscicidal effect against *Bulinus* species and *Biomphalaria* species of snails. Crude extracts of these plants caused death of the snails at varying concentrations. The best results in terms of toxicity to the intermediate host snail were exhibited by *Croton macrostachyus* seed, followed by *Croton macrostachyus* leaf. Prolonging the time of exposure was also found to increase the killing ability on half of the plant extracts.

Keywords: Molluscicidal; LC50; LC90; schistosomiasis; plant extracts; *Croton microstachyus*; *Cissus quadrangularis*; *Biophlaria*; *Bulinus*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Schistosomiasis or Bilharzia is a debilitating disease caused by parasitic worms of the genus *Schistosoma*, a blood fluke. The disease schistosomiasis has great public health and economic importance in the developing world and it is the second most prevalent tropical disease in Africa next to malaria. It is estimated by World Health Organization (WHO), that about 500-600 million people in 74 tropical and sub-tropical countries are at risk of contracting the disease. More than 200 million people in these countries are already infected, 85% of whom live in sub-Saharan Africa where *S. haematobium*, *S. intercalatum* and *S. mansoni* are endemic [1]. In Eritrea, study findings in 2015 showed that Schistosomiasis is endemic in three zones (Zones Debub, Anseba and Maekel). Schistosomiasis infected children were found in 66 of the 176 schools investigated, with an overall prevalence of 4.3% [2]. Schistosomiasis is caused by digenetic trematodes belonging to phylum Platyhelminthes, super family Schistosomatoidea, and genus *Schistosoma*. It is usually attributed to three species, subdivided into intestinal *Schistosoma mansoni* and *Schistosoma japonicum* and urinary *Schistosoma haematobium* types, according to the site preferred by the adult worms [3].

In humans, these blood flukes reside in the mesenteric and vesicle venules. They have a life span of many years and produce large numbers of eggs daily, which must pass through the gut and bladder tissues on their way to the lumens of the excretory organs. Many of the eggs remain in the host tissues, inducing immunologically

mediated granulomatous inflammation and fibrosis. Heavy worm burdens may produce hepatosplenic and urinary tract diseases depending on the species preference of infection.

The different species of *Schistosoma* have different types of snails serving as their intermediate hosts; these hosts include: *Biomphalaria* for *S. mansoni*, *Oncomelania* for *S. japonicum*, *Tricula (Neotricula aperta)* for *S. mekongi*, and *Bulinus* for *S. haematobium* and *S. intercalatum*. The species snails can be identified by the shape of the outer shell. Simple regional keys are available for the determination of most species [4,5].

Despite the devastating effects of schistosomiasis, a safe and biodiversity friendly agent is not yet available. The synthetic molluscicidal agents used conventionally to control the snails have many setbacks besides being very expensive.

Therefore, the objective of this study is to identify, evaluate and compare molluscicidal activities of different solvent extracts of *Croton macrostachyus* leaf, seeds and *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf against the snails *Biomphalaria* and *Bulinus* species, the intermediate hosts of schistosomiasis.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Material

The plants parts (Leaf, Seed) used in this study were collected and authenticated by a

Taxonomist, Eritrean Institute of Technology (EIT), Mainefhi, Eritrea. They were then left to air dry for 4 days. Air dried and powdered plant material (100 - 200 g) was macerated in various solvents (water, ethanol, chloroform, and petroleum ether) for 3 days on occasional shaking. After filtration, the solvents were evaporated using a rota vapour at controlled temperature and pressure. The extracts were kept in tightly closed bottles at room temperature until required for molluscicidal activity.

2.2 Snail Materials

The experimental snails, *Biomphalaria* sp., intermediate host of *S. mansoni*, and *Bulinus* sp. intermediate host of *S. haematobium* and *S. intercalatum* were collected from one of the Schistosoma endemic areas of Eritrea, Sub-zone Adi-quala (Semomo Dam) about 86 Km., south of the capital city Asmara, from water streams running below the dam. The snails were identified by a taxonomist in accordance with standard identification keys [6], and were left to acclimatize to laboratory conditions in an aquarium at room temperature for 4-5 days in a media provided before testing.

2.3 Molluscicidal Activity

The WHO working guideline and the standard test procedures were followed for the evaluation of the plant molluscicidal activity [7,8].

Preliminary screening of the plants for molluscicidal activity was carried out using a bioassay that employed 10 adult snails of *each genera* submerged for 24 hours at room temperature in beakers containing five hundred millilitres of 1000 ppm solution of the water extract of each plant. Control experiments were performed in distilled water or 1% surfactant (Tween 80) without the extracts and ran in parallel with the test experiments. Mortality was recorded at twenty four hours. Dead snails were identified by body discoloration, bleeding, and lack of movement and body contraction in response to mechanical stimuli [9]. Extracts with at least 50% mortality after this test were considered potent and were used in more detailed studies as described below.

From a stock solution of 1000 ppm, serial dilutions of various concentrations ranging from

10 to 250 ppm (with 10 ppm interval) were prepared for each plant extract, according their estimated activity, in 500 ml of total solution. Each concentration contained 10 snails in three replicates in a container of 500 ml capacity, amounting to 30 experimental snails per concentration and ten more snails in separate distilled water or 1% surfactant (Tween80) that served as control.

The snails were exposed for 24, 36 and 48 hours at room temperature in the extract solution. They were, then, washed 2 times in distilled water and kept in extract free water for another 24 hours recovery period. Mortality was determined by the absence of movement, failure of the flesh portion to withdraw into the shell upon mechanical stimuli (probe), colour change and at times when bleeding was observed. Mortality (%) was plotted against the respective concentration, and the concentration of the extract killing 50% (LC50) and 90% (LC90) of the snails was then determined.

2.4 Data Analysis

For determination of the mortality rate per concentration, regression (probe) was used. And ANOVA was also used for comparison of the killing activities of the different solvent extracts within and among each plant material. Two software, IBM SPSS 20 and Microsoft office Excel 2007 were used for every statistical analysis. P value <0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Preliminary Screening Test

All extract of the different plants materials was found to kill 100% of the snails on both species up to 24 hours of exposure.

3.2 Experimental Results

The molluscicidal activity of the different plant materials, *Croton macrostachyus* leaf, seed, and *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf were evaluated with different solvent extracts, (water, ethanol, petroleum ether and chloroform.). In addition, comparison of the different solvent extracts within each plant material had been assessed as follows:

Fig. 1. Molluscicidal activity of *Croton macrostachyus* leaf against *Bulinus*

The evaluation and comparison of the different solvent extracts in *C. macrostachyus* leaf against *Bulinus* species shows, chloroform extract has the highest molluscicidal activity. And there is a significant difference, with p -value $1.26E-05 (P < 0.05)$

Fig. 2. Molluscicidal activity of *Croton macrostachyus* leaf on *Biomphalaria*

The evaluation and comparison of the different solvent extracts of *C. macrostachyus* leaf against *Biomphalaria* species shows chloroform extract has the highest molluscicidal activity. And there is a significant difference among the solvent extracts with p -value $6.23E-15 (p < 0.05)$

Fig. 3. Molluscicidal activity of *Croton macrostachyus* seed on *Bulinus* species

The evaluation and comparison of *C. macrostachyus* seed against *Bulinus* species of different solvent extracts shows that, chloroform extract has the highest molluscicidal activity and there is a significant difference among solvent extract with p -value $0.00149 (p < 0.05)$

Fig. 4. Molluscicidal activity of *Croton macrostachyus* seed on *Biomphalaria* species
 The evaluation and comparison of *Croton macrostachyus* seed of the different solvent extracts against *Biomphalaria* species shows, ethanol extract has the highest molluscicidal activity. There is also a significant difference among the solvent extracts, with p-value 3.69E-07(p<0.05)

Fig. 5. Molluscicidal activity of *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf on *Bulinus* species
 Evaluation and comparison of *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf against *Bulinus* species with different solvent extracts shows, ethanol extract has the highest molluscicidal activity. There is also a significant difference among the solvent extracts, with p-value 0.000441(p<0.05)

Fig. 6. Molluscicidal activity of *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf on *Biomphalaria* species
 Evaluation and comparison of *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf against *Biomphalaria* species with different solvent extracts shows, ethanol has the highest molluscicidal activity. There is also a significant difference among solvent extract, with P-value 4.2E-10 (p<0.05)

3.3 Determination of LC50, LC90 of the Different Solvent Extract of Each Plant Material against Both Species of Snails

The lethal concentration of the different solvent extracts of each plant materials

against both *Bulinus* and *Biomphalaria* species was determined at 24, 36, 48 hours of exposure. The effects of increase in time of exposure with molluscicidal activity have also been assessed as follows (Tables 1-4).

Table 1. The LC50s of the plant materials in each solvent extract against *Bulinus* species

Solvent extract		LC50 in ppm(mg/lit)			
		24 hrs	36 hrs	48 hrs	p-value
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> leaf	water	94.207	50.585	32.557	.00253
	Ethanol	34.114	31.304	17.793	0.037498
	Petroleum ether	43.287	29.06	23.5	0.085503
	chloroform	23.029	14.747	11.665	0.198465
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> seed	water	46.996	30.502	17.813	0.002144
	Ethanol	29.12	4.99	2.679	0.001546
	Petroleum ether	35.116	20.662	16.826	0.122485
	chloroform	15.558	11.316	10.793	0.538087
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> leaf	water	116.524	83.981	63.315	0.046143
	Ethanol	40.834	27.639	15.466	0.266469
	Petroleum ether	93.893	61.969	26.908	0.018808
	chloroform	118.849	78.043	60.585	0.070202

Table 2. The LC90s of the plant materials in each solvent extract against *Bulinus* species

Solvent extract		LC50 in ppm(mg/lit)			
		24 hrs	36 hrs	48 hrs	p-value
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> leaf	Water	143.637	105.834	61.46	0.00253
	Ethanol	74.285	60.747	39.224	0.037498
	Petroleum ether	74.361	51.437	45.927	0.085503
	Chloroform	48.214	41.491	19.774	0.198465
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> seed	Water	71.221	50.566	35.245	0.002144
	Ethanol	52.919	18.376	15.104	0.001546
	Petroleum ether	57.609	49.378	37.484	0.122485
	Chloroform	27.126	26.434	20.125	0.532087
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> leaf	Water	184.074	143.118	110.101	0.046143
	Ethanol	71.979	67.036	57.3	0.266469
	Petroleum ether	148.399	175.049	77.152	0.018808
	Chloroform	179.921	151.085	123.784	0.070202

Table 3. The LC50s of the plant materials in each solvent extract against *Biomphalaria* species

Solvent extract		LC50 in ppm(mg/lit)			
		24 hrs	36 hrs	48 hrs	p-value
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> leaf	water	211.965	205.347	169.682	0.23584
	Ethanol	108.838	93.431	89.216	0.196997
	Petroleum ether	72.331	38.49	33.396	0.000504
	chloroform	16.167	11.203	10.122	0.348403
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> seed	water	137.055	103.46	90.566	0.001144
	Ethanol	38.211	18.974	15.344	0.276795
	Petroleum ether	154.096	136.984	123.659	0.66E05
	chloroform	64.575	69.891	72.441	0.00273
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> leaf	water	152.717	135.799	117.582	0.168442
	Ethanol	43.224	28.2014	22.902	0.185203
	Petroleum ether	220.537	170.524	146.487	0.003682
	chloroform	182.744	137.396	111.986	0.002126

Table 4. The LC90s of the plant materials in each solvent extract against *Biomphalaria*

Solvent extract		LC90 in ppm(mg/lit)			
		24 hrs	36 hrs	48 hrs	p-value
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> leaf	water	277.69	268.54	242.531	0.23584
	Ethanol	141.414	128.617	114.239	0.196997
	Petroleum ether	101.404	63.544	56.377	0.000504
	chloroform	26.391	25.418	19.54	0.348403
<i>Croton macrostachyus</i> seed	water	167.99	150.511	137.605	0.001144
	Ethanol	61.693	45.049	36.625	0.276795
	Petroleum ether	216.526	203.767	193.098	2.66E.05
	chloroform	138.541	117.814	123.01	0.00273
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> leaf	water	194.657	174.05	171.792	0.168442
	Ethanol	81.939	63.743	46.69	0.185203
	Petroleum ether	289.689	206.465	209.88	0.003682
	chloroform	240.96	184.492	167.568	0.002126

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Evaluation of the different solvent extract of each plant revealed that chloroform extract of *Croton macrostachyus* seed (Table 1 and 2) has shown the highest molluscicidal activity against *Bulinus* species after 24 hours of exposure, with LC50 of 15.558 ppm, LC90 of 27.126 ppm. Chloroform extract of *Croton macrostachyus* leaf has the highest molluscicidal activity (Tables 3 and 4) against *Biomphalaria* species, with LC50 of 16.167 ppm, LC90 of 26.391 ppm.

In general, the comparison of the plant materials, plant extract of *Croton macrostachyus* seed had the highest molluscicidal activity. On this experimental study the molluscicidal activity of the different plant extracts ranges from 2.679 ppm (LC50 of ethanol extract of *Croton macrostachyus* seed after 48 hours exposure) to 289.689 ppm (LC90 of petroleum ether extract of *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf after 24 hours exposure).

Comparison of molluscicidal activity of the different solvent extract in each plants material was assessed using ANOVA, and a significant difference was shown in the plants materials, with p-value less than 0.05. Accordingly, in *Croton macrostachyus* leaf chloroform extract against both *Biomphalaria* and *Bulinus* spp. with LC50, LC90 values of 16.167, 26.391 ppm and 23.029, 48.214 ppm respectively (Tables 1,2,3,4); exhibited the highest molluscicidal activity. In *Croton macrostachyus* seed, chloroform extract against *Bulinus* with LC50, LC90 values of 15.558,27.126 ppm (Tables 1,2) and ethanol extract against *Biomphalaria* with LC50, LC90 value of 38.211,61.693 ppm respectively (Tables 3,4) were found to have the

highest molluscicidal activities. Regarding *Cissus quadrangularis* leaf, ethanol extract against both *Biomphalaria* and *Bulinus* spp. with LC50, LC90 values of 43.224, 89.939 ppm and 40.334, 71.979 ppm respectively were also found to have the highest molluscicidal activities (Tables 1,2,3,4).

The effect of exposure time on the molluscicidal activity of each plant material was also assessed (Tables 1,2,3,4) and the result showed that there is a significant difference between time of exposure and molluscicidal activity, on 50% of the extracts, with p-value less than 0.05.

According to WHO, crude organic extract should present LC90 below 20 ppm to be considered as good molluscicidal candidate for direct application in infected water [10]. However, it is suggested that extracts between 20 and 100 ppm would contain some amount of very active components [11]. Another WHO publication, recommends that plant extracts showing LC50 values less than 40 ppm may be employed directly against mollusc population [12].

In this study, 67% percent of the different plant extracts have shown LC90 between 20 and 100 ppm at 24 hours exposure against *Bulinus* species, and about 34% of the plant extracts have shown LC90 between 20 and 100 ppm against *Biomphalaria* species. Half (50%) of the extracts have LC50 less than 40 ppm against *Bulinus* and 25% against *Biomphalaria* species. This shows that the plant materials have a good molluscicidal activity which is helpful to be implemented on the ground or to make a base for further researches.

The findings of the present study indicate that, in general, the exposure of the plant materials to *Bulinus* species is more potent than to *Biomphalaria* species, most probably this could be due to the difference in the morphological features of their shell, in which the shell of *Biomphalaria* species more prominently cover their body.

Further research work is needed to isolate the active molecule or standardization of the active plant extract with respect to its molluscicidal activity.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It is not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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